

Master thesis on

**"AN ANALYSIS OF RECRUITMENT & SELECTION
PROCESS AT DABUR INDIA LIMITED"**

**For the partial fulfilment of the requirement
for the award of the degree of**

MASTERS OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION

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Certificate

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STUDENT DECLARATION

I **Subhasini Singh** bearing University Admission No. **20GSOB2010005**, of Galgotias University, Greater Noida Enrolled as student of MBA in Dual Specialization at Galgotias University Greater Noida, solemnly declare that the Master Thesis Report Titled, **“AN ANALYSIS OF RECRUITMENT & SELECTION PROCESS AT DABUR INDIA LIMITED”** embodies the results of original research work carried out by me and the same has not been submitted in any form partially or fully for award of any diploma or degree of this or any other University/Institute.

Subhasini Singh

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CONTENT

	Page No.
Student Declaration	3
Executive Summary.....6	
Acknowledgement	8
Abstract.....	9
Chapter 1- Introduction to the present study.....	11
Chapter 2- Review of literature	27
Chapter 3- Research Methodology.....	58
Chapter 4- Research Analysis	100
Chapter 5- Research Findings	115
Chapter 6- Conclusion	117

/References 118

Annexure1.....119

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

As in case of any other functional area like marketing, production or finance, the work personnel department has also to be planned. Planning in the personnel area is mainly concerned with crystallizing from where the right type of people can be secured for future anticipated vacancies.

Manpower planning is the process by which management determines how the organization should move from its current manpower position to its desired manpower position. Through planning, management strives to have the right number and the right kinds of people, at the right places, at the right time, doing things, which result in the growth and success of both- the organization and the individual. The manpower planning is one of the basic steps in the recruitment and selection procedure.

Recruitment and Selection is the process wherein the organisation finds the best candidate among the vast array of candidates. The function that locates the sources where from the required human resources can be available and to attract them towards the organisation is known as **recruitment**.

Selection can be defined as the process wherein the organisation has to select a small lot of people who are useful to the organisation in terms of their capabilities and their qualifications. The main aim of organisation at this stage is to have a well-equipped manpower efficient enough to handle all the tasks gracefully.

This project entitled "***Recruitment and Selection in Dabur India Ltd (DIL)***" aims at studying the recruitment and selection procedure undertaken at this ever growing organisation. The project gives a brief idea as to how the whole process works. Every organisation has different policies, at times unique and it is very rare that the policy of one organisation matches to the policies of another organisation.

It is true that the success of any organisation depends upon the old dictum: ***right person for the right job***. At the same time it is all the more important to have right and tested combination of recruitment and selection policies to attract, select and appoint a desired lot and replenish it from time to time. The transformation from a family concern to FMCG industry has tested the recruitment and selection policies and the organisation. The sustainability and success of this living legend over hundred years has proved that the strategies adopted by this multinational are true to its needs and requirement. DIL has a strong work force of 2,500 employees.

DIL has succeeded over hundred years because it still follows the basic dictum and is being guided by the vision and the age-old the principles which are followed religiously.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This Master Thesis Project was a great chance for learning Professional development. Therefore, I consider myself lucky as I was provided with an opportunity to be a part of it. I am also grateful for having a chance to work with such ideal people and professionals who guided me through this Master Thesis Project. I convey my sincere gratitude to my mentor Mrs. RatnaManjary Das, assistant professor, Galgotias University. Without her kind direction and proper guidelines this report would have been a little success. In every phase of this report her supervision and guidance shaped this report to be completed perfectly. I would also thank my faculty members who guided me during my master thesis project and participated and contributed equally to complete my tasks with ease. I perceive this opportunity as a big milestone in my career development. I will strive to use these gained knowledge and skills in the best possible way, and will continue to work on the improvement, in order to attain desired career objectives.

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ABSTRACT

Human Resources is the department which leads the development and upgrade of the corporate culture. The common corporate culture is crucial for the global organization. The organization cannot act the same way around the Globe when the corporate culture is different. On the other hand, the development of the common corporate culture is difficult. The nations are different. The HR Role is to set up the international team, which develops the unified corporate culture and corporate values. They have to understand roots of the common corporate culture and how they are expected to behave globally. The employees and managers have to communicate globally with colleagues around the Globe. The unified way of communication, the approach to problem solving and identification with the organization make global decisions easier. HR should be the first global function. It has to introduce the globally managed HR processes focused on the development of the global talents and bringing the unified approach. The performance management and the talent management are usually the first globally managed HR processes. The unified and globally managed performance management process helps to manage the performance of individual businesses in countries and helps to identify the future global leaders for the organization. The global Human Resources is able to identify best talents in the organization, and move talents to different countries. It is not easy to introduce the global mobility, but the global organization needs global managers, who are able to run difficult projects over continents. The identification of global leaders needs a strong global Human Resources. The HR Professionals have to be trained in global policies, and they have to be managed from different Centers of Excellence around the Globe. The globalization demands new skills and competencies. Managers have to think globally, and they have to find advantages for the organization on the global basis. They have to be able to negotiate with partners from a different cultural background. HR has to adapt its processes, procedures, policies and training to ease the life of managers into the global world of the organization.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

RECRUITMENT

Recruitment and selection are the most important functions in an organisation because with the help of these functions the management selects the best available candidate from a batch of them. The organisations, in this growing competitive world, need to have the best of the manpower so as to have an edge over its competitors.

According to Flippo, *"Recruitment is the process of searching for prospective employees and stimulating and encouraging them to apply for jobs in an organisation."*

In the words of Yoder, *"Recruitment is a process to discover the sources of manpower to meet the requirements of the staffing schedule and to employ effective measures for attracting that manpower in adequate numbers to facilitate effective selection of an efficient working force."*

The recruitment needs can be classified into-

- Planned.
- Anticipated.

- Unexpected.

Planned need arise from changes in the organisation and retirement policy. These occur due the expected changes in the organisation so the management can make a proper policy for it.

Anticipated need refer to the movements in personnel which an organisation can predict by studying the trends in the internal and external environments.

Resignations, deaths, accidents and illness result in to the unexpected needs.

FEATURES:

- Recruitment is a process or a series of activities rather than a single event.
- It is a linking activity as it brings together the employers and employees.
- It is positive process because in this activity the employers want to have the maximum number of job seekers so as to have a wider scope for choice ultimately leading in spotting right persons for job.
- It is an important function as it makes it possible to acquire the number and type of persons required for the effective functioning of the organisation.

- It is an on going function in all the organisations, but the volume and nature of recruitment varies with the size, nature and environment of the organisation.
- It is a complex process because a number of factors affect it --the nature of the job offered, image of the organisation, organisational policies, working conditions etc.

SOURCES OF RECRUITMENT:

The various sources of recruitment are -

- **Internal Sources**: Include-
 - Present Employees who can be transferred or given promotions.
 - The retired and retrenched employees who want to return to the company.
 - Dependents and relatives of the deceased and disabled employees.
- **External Sources**: Consist of-
 - Press advertisements.
 - Campus Interviews.
 - Placement Agencies.
 - Recommendations.
 - Recruitment at factory gate.

□ Employment Exchanges.

During my short stint at DIL, it was observed that the recruitment need of DIL is diversified. It needs persons who have knowledge of use, processing of natural ingredients of number of varied products, technical know-how of latest industrial technical knowledge, and computer applications to pharmaceutical industry to manual workers. The importance of the process could be understood that the present work force of DIL is 2,500 employees. Hence, the recruitment and selection procedure should match the complexities of the need and at the same should commensurate with the complex need of the organisation

SELECTION

Selection is the process of choosing the best candidate out of the all the applicants. In this process, relevant information about the applicants is collected through a series of steps so as to evaluate their suitability for the job to be filled.

It is the process of matching the qualifications with those required for the job so that the candidate can be entrusted with the task that matches with his credibility. It is a process of weeding out unsuitable candidates and finally identifying the most suitable candidates.

This process divides the candidates into two categories-the suitable ones and the unsuitable ones. The suitable people prove to be the asset for the organisation.

Selection is a negative process because in this process the management tries to minimise the number of people at each step so that the final decision can be in the light of all the factors and at the end of it best candidate is selected. Selected candidate the has to pass through the following stages-

- Preliminary Interview.
- Application Form.
- Selection Test.
- Selection Interview.
- Physical Examination.
- Reference Check.
- Final Approval.
- Employment.

Preliminary Interview is the initial screening done to weed out the undesirable candidates. This is mainly a sorting process in which the prospective candidates are given the necessary information about the nature of the job and the organisation. Necessary information about the candidate is also taken. If the candidate is found suitable then he is selected for further screening else he is dropped. This stage saves the time and effort of both the company and the candidate. It avoids unnecessary waiting for the candidate and waste of money for further processing of an unsuitable candidate.

Application Form is a traditional and widely used device for collecting information from candidates. This form asks the candidates to fill up the necessary information regarding their basic information like name, address, references, date of birth, marital status, educational qualifications, experience, salary structure in previous organisation and other such information. This form is of great help because the scrutiny of this form helps to weed out candidate who are lacking in education, experience or any other criterion provided by the organisation. It also helps in formulation of questions, which will be asked in the interview. These forms can also be stored for future references thus maintaining a databank of the applicants.

Selection Interview involves the interaction of the employer and the employee. Selection involves a personal, observational and face-to-face appraisal of candidates for employment. It is an essential element of the selection procedure. The information obtained through application form and test can be crosschecked in the interview.

INTRODUCTION TO DABUR

Dabur India Limited came into existence over 100 years ago in 1884 at Calcutta. The founder, Dr.S.K.Burman, was a practicing allopathic doctor. At that time Malaria, Cholera and Plague were the common diseases. He was a physician who brought ayurvedic medicines to the masses of Bengal. Initially established as a proprietary firm for the manufacture of chemicals and ayurvedic drugs it was later on 19th November 1930 incorporated as private limited company. Late Shri

C.L.Burman, son of late Dr S.K. Burman and his son late Shri P.C.Burman in the name of Dr S.K.Burman Pvt.Ltd. to expand the operations by setting up production facilities at Garia and Narendrapur, West Bengal and Daburgram, Bihar.

Dabur (Dr.S.K.Burman) Pvt. Ltd. was merged with Vidogum and Chemicals Ltd. w.e.f. 1st July 1985 and the amalgamated company was renamed **DABUR INDIA LIMITED** and a fresh certificate of incorporation was issued to that effect. In 1970, the bulk of manufacturing facilities were shifted from West Bengal to Faridabad in Haryana.

In 1975, vidogum and chemicals were incorporated in technical collaboration with Unipekin AG (Switzerland) for the manufacture of edible grade and industrial grade Guar gum powder at Alwar in Rajasthan.

In 1977, a modern automated plant was set up in Sahibabad (U.P.) for the manufacture of Chyawanprash, Asavrishtas, Hair oil, Tooth powders, Hajmola, and other Ayurvedic specialties. Certification for production of toiletries and food grade products was issued on 13th October 1986 by the registrar of Delhi and Haryana to the company, Dabur Private Limited, a closely held Public Limited Company.

It was incorporated as a Private Ltd. Company in the name of Dabur (Dr. S.K. Burman) Pvt. Ltd. From a humble beginning in 1884, a manufacture of traditional medicine in Calcutta, Dabur has come a long way to become a multifaceted multinational, multi-product, modern Indian corporation with a global presence. It now enjoys the distinction of being the 2nd largest FMCG Company and is praised to become a true Indian Multinational.

The main plant was set up in Sahibabad (U.P.) in 1977 for manufacturing of Chyawanprash, hair oil, tooth powder, hajmola and other ayurvedic medicines and food products etc. Dabur's main line of business is in the sphere of Health care,

Personal care and Beauty care. Its strength lies in natural and herbal preparations.

Dabur's corporate philosophy has always been ahead of its time. The founder's initial success was mainly due to his direct main campaigns- a technique that became very popular nearly a century later. The company was one of the earlier Indian companies to have fully equipped R & D lab as early as in 1919. Today, the company has its own mainframes and computers are a way of life here.

Dabur is also an ISO 9002 certified company. The certification was obtained in 1995 by SGS YARSLEY international services Limited U.K. Dabur's revenue today exceed Rs.800 crores with plans to achieve Rs.2, 000 crores by year 2003. Dabur has 34,000 shareholders with market capitalization of over Rs.1, 400 crores.

Dabur has 11 manufacturing plants in India and Nepal and a licensee in the Middle East. It has manufacturing base in Egypt also. The company has over 4,000 employees with around 1,500 looking after sales and marketing functions.

The Indian market is being served through a transactional network of sales offices and carrying and forwarding agents. The company has its offices in London, New York and Moscow. Dabur products are being exported to around 50 countries. Dabur portfolio is exceeding 500 products of FMCG and health care products.

The Board of Directors of Dabur India Limited (DIL) met on July 23, 2003 to consider the unaudited financials of the company for the first quarter that ended on June 30, 2003. Company has recorded a growth of 36 per cent in its net profit per cent growth in its turnover during April-June 2003.

DABUR OVER THE YEARS

More than a century ago, a young doctor started with a vision to provide

innovative and affordable health care products to Indian masses. Thus, was born an organisation today known as **Dabur India Limited**. The **twelve hundred crores** corporate today started with a small dispensary at Calcutta, the noble thoughts of Dr.S.K.Burman being the main source of inspiration behind the project. From that humble beginning, the company has grown into India's leading manufacturer of consumer health care, personal care and food products. This phenomenal progress has seen many milestones, some of which are mentioned below:

- **1884:** Dr.S.K.Burman lays the foundation of what is known as Dabur India Limited. Started from a small shop at Calcutta, he began a direct mailing system to send his medicines to even the smallest of villages in Bengal. The brand name Dabur is derived from the words "DA" for *Daktar* or doctor and "BUR" from Burman.
- **1896:** As the demand for Dabur products grows, Dr. Burman felt the need for mass production for some of his medicines. He set up a small manufacturing plant at Garhai near Calcutta.
- **Early 1900s:** The next generation of Burman's take a conscious decision to enter the Ayurvedic medicines market, as they believe that it is only through ayurveda that the healthcare needs of poor Indians can be met.
- **1919:** The search for processes to suit mass production of ayurvedic medicines without compromising on basic ayurvedic principles lead to the setting up of the first Research and Development laboratory at Dabur..
- **1920s:**A-manufacturing facility for Ayurvedic Medicines is set up at Narendrapur and Daburgram. Dabur expands its distribution network to Bihar and northeast.

- **1936:** Dabur India (Dr. S.K.Burman) Pvt.Ltd. is incorporated.
- **1940:** Dabur diversifies into personal care products with the launch of its Dabur Amla Hair Oil. This perfumed hair oil catches the imagination of the common man and film stars alike and becomes the largest hair oil brand in India.
- **1949:** Dabur Chyawanprash is launched in a tin pack and becomes the first branded Chyawanprash of India.
- **1956:** Dabur buys its first computer. Accounts and stock keeping are one of the first operations to be computerized.
- **1970:** Dabur expands its personal care portfolio by adding oral care products. Dabur Lal Dant Manjan is launched and captures the Indian rural market.
- **1972:** Dabur shifts base to Delhi from Calcutta. Starts production from a hired manufacturing facility at Faridabad.
- **1978:** Dabur launches the Hajmola tablets. This is the first time that a classical ayurvedic medicine is branded from Shudhabardhak bati to Hajmola tablets.
- **1979:** The Dabur Research Foundation (DRF), an independent company is set up to spearhead Dabur's multi-faceted research. Commercial production starts at Sahibabad. This is one of the largest and most modern production facilities for ayurvedic medicines in India at this time.
- **1984:** The Dabur brand turns 100 but is still young enough to experiment

with new offerings in the market.

- **1986:** Dabur becomes a public Limited company through reverse merger with Vidogum Limited, and is re-christened Dabur India Limited.
- **1989:** Hajmola Candy is launched and captures the imagination of children and establishes a large market share.
- **1992:** Dabur enters into a joint venture with Agrolimen of Spain for manufacturing and marketing confectionery items such as bubble gums in India.
- **1993:** Dabur set up the oncology formulation plant at Baddi, Himachal Pradesh.
- **1994:** Dabur India Limited comes out with its first public issue at a premium of Rs.85 per share. The issue is subscribed over 21 times.
- **1994:** Dabur enters the oncology (anti-cancer) market with the launch of Intaxel (Pacitaxel). Dabur becomes only the second company in the world to launch this product. The Dabur Research Foundation develops the unique eco-friendly process of extracting the drug from the leaves of the Asian Yew Tree.
- **1995:** Dabur enters into a joint venture with Osem of Israel for food and Bongrain of France for cheese and other dairy products.
- **1996:** Dabur launches Real fruit juices, which heralds the company's entry into the processed food market.

- **1997:** The foods division is created, comprising of real fruit juices and Homemade cooking paste to form the core of this division's product portfolio.
- **1998:** Project STARS (Strive To Achieve Record Successes) is initiated by the company to achieve accelerated growth in the coming years. The scope of this project is strategic, structural and operational changes to enables efficiencies and improves growth rates.
- **1998:** The Burman family hands over the reins of the company to a professional, Mr. Ninu Khanna joins Dabur, as the Chief Executive Officer.
- **1999-2000:** Dabur achieves the Rs.1000 crores turnover mark.
- **2001-2002:** Launched Amla Light, new flavors in Real Juices-grapes, guava, apple active, orange active, homemade pappad, Vatika- an anti-dandruff shampoo.
- **2002:** New launches homemade coconut milk (in south), Tang, Tomato puree, Vatika light.
- **2003:** Dabur achieves Rs.1,232 crores turnover mark with an increase of 6 per cent. Turnover of FMCG reaches to Rs 1048.5crores

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

QUALITY OBJECTS

- ❖ To focus on customers successfully and to strive to meet their needs and requirements.
- ❖ To manufacture effective health care products at competitive prices and to improve the Quality of Life of common masses.
- ❖ To implement and emphasise on systems to ensure prevention of errors rather than detection of errors.
- ❖ To ensure global competitiveness by striving to achieve Current Good Manufacturing Practices (CGMP).
- ❖ To ensure safety in all operations and to follow the systems in all areas of operations.
- ❖ To continually train people to build up and upgrade skills and expertise and to involve them to become committed to the quality process.
- ❖ To reduce wastages within the organisation and increase productivity.

IMPORTANT STRATEGIES ADOPTED

- ❖ "Developing to built" philosophy for HR personnel.
- ❖ Shifting to zonal set up of sales and marketing to facilitate better distribution.
- ❖ Adopting contribution enhancement plan for performance management.
- ❖ Empowering employees through Employee Stock Purchase Option Plan.
- ❖ Backward integration strategy in Ayurvedic Products by engaging in plantation of herbs needed for the production of Ayurvedic Products.
- ❖ Continuous enhancement of automation.
- ❖ Continuous emphasis on Research & Development (DRF i.e. Dabur Research Foundation is a separate company working in collaboration with Dabur solely for the purpose of R&D)

PERSONNEL DEVELOPMENT IN DABUR

- Personnel department is headed by Vice- President (HR)
- Functions of Vice President (HR)
- Personnel administration
- Recruitment and Promotion
- Industrial Relations
- Human Resource Group
- Human Resource Development

- General Administration and Welfare
- Public Relations
- Security/Fire Vigilance
- Medical Services
- Implementation Of Official Language Policy (Hindi)
- Land Acquisition

The above functions are grouped under different General Managers/Deputy General Managers. These executives provide support to Vice President (HR) on different issues, which arise in Headquarter/regional offices and field. Vice President (HR) has the responsibility of keeping the Board of Directors informed on the above mentioned personnel activities and also on Industrial Relations. In addition to this, he is also expected up date senior officials in their respective areas.

HUMAN RESOURCE FUNCTIONS

- Recruitment and selection.
- Performance Appraisal.
- Training and Development.
- Promotion, Transfer, Seperation.
- General administration & Welfare.
- Security.
- Public Relations.
- Industrial Relations.

HUMAN RESOURCE DEPARTMENT

LITERATURE REVIEW

RECRUITMENT PROCESS

DETERMINING MANPOWER REQUIREMENT

A Recruitment analysis is conducted depending on the job profile. A well- designed and comprehensive recruitment analysis is invaluable to an organization’s well being. Recruitment analysis basically ensures the availability of the right resources in the right place to match the future organizational needs. Recruitment analysis can be defined as the process of ensuring the right number of qualified people, into the right job at the right time to deliver the results in an efficient and effective manner. Recruitment is the process of searching for and attracting qualified candidates to apply for the positions that are available. Whether your company is heavily recruiting or in the midst of a hiring freeze, you should always have a recruiting plan. Plans will vary based on hiring volume and type of position, but you

should articulate a standard strategy of how you recruit and fill positions. A well-defined recruiting strategy will help ensure that the right employees are in place when needed.

The objectives are:

1. To maintain the required quantity and quality of human resources required.
2. To forecast the turnover/attrition rates.
3. To plan to meet organizational human resource needs at the time of expansion or diversification.
4. To make contingent plans to handle sudden requirements and situations of shortfall.

SOURCING RESUMES:

There various methods of recruiting are given below:

1. **INTERNAL SOURCES:** Many organizations try and identify employees from within the organization to be groomed to take on higher responsibilities. Internal recruiting is beneficial, as workers know the firm culture; managers already know the workers and the internal advancement can motivate the employees. In today's technologically advanced world many organizations depend on their HRIS. Some of the internal sources are:
 - a. **Job Postings:** Openings are published on bulletin boards (electronic or hard copy) or in lists available to all employees. Interested employees must reply within a specified number of days and they may or may not have to obtain the consent of their immediate supervisors. This is the process used by managers to provide information about job openings to employees.
 - b. **Employee Referrals:** Employees working with an organization recommend their friends or acquaintances for vacant positions in

the organization. This source is usually one of the most effective and reliable methods of recruiting because many qualified people especially for the lower and middle management are reached at a very low cost to the company.

- c. **Contract Management:** Temporary worker pools are created to meet out the unexpected demand of the human resource in the organization.
- d. **Previous Employees:** Organizations can recruit their previous employees as they can prove to be reliable as they already know about the organization policies and procedures and need not to be trained and easily adjust to the environment.

2. EXTERNAL SOURCES: To meet demands for talent brought about by business growth to seek fresh ideas or to replace employees who leave organizations periodically turn to the outside labor market. Managers look outside the firm for people who have not worked at the firm before. The following methods are adopted to recruit people form outside:

- a. **Press Advertisements:** Advertisements are placed in both newspapers and trade journals and three factors influence the choice of this media-cost, profile of the readership and circulation. Some factors affecting the design of advertising are:
 - The image of the organization.
 - The nature of the job.
 - The chosen media.
 - The prediction of the target market.

- b. **Walk-INS:** In a walk-in no prior appointment is there, the applicant approaches the organization directly. It is the most common and least expensive approach as in this the job seekers submit unsolicited application letters or resumes and from employees point of view, walk-ins are preferable as they are free from the hassles associated with other methods of recruitment. Direct applications are particularly effective in filling entry-level and unskilled vacancies, some organizations compile pools of potential employees from direct applications for skilled positions.
- c. **Employment Agencies:** Employment agencies now provide occupations for almost all levels in an organization. They are broadly classified into public or state agencies, private agencies and headhunters.
- d. **Job Sites:** Various job sites like Naukri.com, Times jobs.com, Monster.com etc come in very handy in finding candidates with the desired skills.
- e. **Job fairs** - Job fairs typically work best for entry-level candidates, but events targeting diversity and/or specialty careers, e.g. engineers, can be found.
- f. **Corporate Web site** - When job seekers are interested in a company they will go directly to that company's Web site to conduct research and/or look for available jobs. Make sure your Web site's job section makes it easy to find and apply for jobs.

SHORT – LISTING:

Short listing is the transition phase between recruitment and selection. It is the stage where the total number of applicants is reduced to select the group the employer wishes to carry on to the selection phase. Short listing may comprise of several stages depending on the number of application received, the complexity of the job requirements and sophistication of the selection process used by the organization. Short listing comprises of:

1. **KNOWLEDGE OF MATCHING CV's:** First of all the candidates are short listed on the basis of matching the CV's. The CV's or curriculum vitae are universally used and their form is standardized.

Typically a CV comprises of:

- Evidence of Skills, Abilities and Achievements
- Employment History
- Experience
- Education
- Languages

2. **METHODS OF SHORT LISTING:** The most common way to reduce the number of applications by short-listing them by categorizing them to various departments first. Then asking the department heads to shortlist the appropriate candidates accordingly.

3. SHORT-LISTING – THE PROCESS:

- Short listing must be carried out independently by at least two people and ideally, as many of the interview panel as possible.
- Any member of staff, who may prejudice the outcome, should be excluded from short listing.
- Short listing should always be carried out using the person specification so that applications can be measured and assessed against criteria and be made on the basis of fact and not assumptions.
- The use of short-listing form is recommended. The short-listing panel to record individual assessment of each candidate and provide feedback can use short-listing form.
- Short-listing form must be used at the interview stage. Short-listing decisions must be based only on the information contained in the application form and any other supporting information supplied by the candidate. Irrelevant information in the application form should be disregarded.
- The attributes in the person specification must be consistently applied to all candidates irrespective of their gender, ethnic origin, age, socio-economic background, disability, religious or political beliefs, family circumstances, sexual orientation or other irrelevant factors.
- Some information can only be determined at interview stage or as group exercises, presentation, tests, etc.
- After individual assessment of each application, decision of whom to short list must be taken.

Once a short list has been drawn up, candidates should be invited for interview.

In the short listing of candidates the following things should be kept in mind:

- Evidence of skills, abilities and achievements that match the criteria that have been specified as essential for the job as closely as possible.
- Consistency of employment (look for unexplained gaps).
- Qualifications compatible with the dates given.
- Evidence of career development.
- Evidence of industry knowledge.
- Previous employer.

FILTERING:

Filtering techniques are used to reduce the number of applicants and also gather relevant information needed before conducting the interview. Filtering techniques involve different methods, such as:

- Knowledge Based Filtering
- Skill Based Filtering
- Attitudinal/Behavioral Filtering

- **KNOWLEDGE BASED FILTERING:** This method is used when the number of applications is more like in Campus recruitment. The evaluation is done based on candidate's academic qualification, percentage of marks scored and experience level or through simple written tests.

SKILL BASED FILTERING: The tasks and skills that may be assessed using simulation exercises are varied. Different types of simulation exercise include:

- **In-trays:** In-trays or in-baskets involve working from the contents of a manager's in-tray, which typically consist of letters, memos and background information. You may be asked to deal with paperwork and make decisions, balancing the volume of work against a tight schedule.
- **Test of productive thinking:** The tests look at the volume, diversity and originality of your ideas. You are presented with open-ended questions relating to various problems and situations and are asked to generate responses within a time limit.
- **Group exercises:** Group exercises are timed discussions, where a group of participants work together to tackle a work-related problem. Sometimes you are given a particular role within a team, for example the sales manager or personnel manager. There would be assessors, who are not looking for right or wrong answers, but for how you interact with your colleagues within the team.
- **Presentation:** You may be asked to make a formal presentation to a number of assessors either on a topic given in advance or in some cases to interpret and analyze given information and present a case to support a decision.
- **Fact-Finding Exercises:** In a fact-finding exercise, you may be asked to reach a destination starting from only a partial knowledge. Your task is to decide what additional information you need to make the decision and sometimes also to question the assessor to obtain this information.
- **Role-Plays:** In a role-play, you are given a particular role to assume for a certain task. The task will involve dealing with a role player in a certain way and there will be an assessor watching the role-play.

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An interview is a procedure designed to obtain information from a person's oral responses to oral enquiries. Interview is by far the most widely used personnel selection procedure. The interview is the focal point of the recruiting process. Part of the selection process, usually the final portion of an examination, for the purpose of evaluating education, experience, and personal qualifications of the candidates, also known as oral interview. It is a meeting between an eligible and an appointing power in order to discuss appointment to a specific vacancy.

An interview is a conversation between two or more people where [questions](#) are asked to obtain information from the interviewee. Interviews can be divided into two rough types, interviews of assessment and interviews for information.

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A good interview results from

- Proper preparation.
- Identifying the candidate's abilities before discussing the position.
- Asking a series of open – ended questions.
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Good interview questions start with job description (analysis). The job description includes tasks, responsibilities and requirements. Those who currently perform the job should create it. This will reduce the inaccuracies and increase the interviewer's awareness of the actual job duties. It should further:

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THE OVERALL INTERVIEW PROCESS

PRE – INTERVIEW PREPARATION THE INTERVIEW ITSELF THE POST INTERVIEW ASSESSMENT AND DECISION PHASE

THE PRE – INTERVIEW PREPARATORY PHASE: The pre – interview phase includes few things to be done for ensuring effectiveness of the total operation so as to avoid any mistakes, which adversely affects the whole interview process. It states:

- Use the data of job analysis to determine the requirements for effective performance of the job and the criteria by which these may be identified and assessed. These data provide the foundation for the whole selection process.
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- Decide the panel of interviewers. When an interview board is used the membership should be the smallest number necessary to fulfill the task.
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- Produce a coverage plan designed to provide the maximum possible significant information.

THE INTERVIEW:

The interview process should:

- Concentrate initially on establishing a sympathetic, productive atmosphere to encourage candidates to talk freely.
- Begin with introduction and a brief explanation of the purpose and scope of the interview.
- Follow the broad chronological, systematic coverage plan throughout in order to ensure a comprehensive coverage. Deviations are likely to create gaps in the information obtained.
- In board interviews arrange for each interviewer to interview in turn.
- Pay utmost attention to the form of question, i.e.:
 - Concentrate on acquiring as much evidence as possible of potential ability to do the required job, based on the facts of past behavior and achievements.
 - In general avoid hypothetical questions, especially those which have no bearing on the job. They can only produce hypothetical answers.
 - Use a simple open question form which does not imply answers.
- Be constantly alert to possible effects of the interviewee's non-verbal behavior and manner and possibility of misinterpretation of intentions by candidates. Be a little sympathetic and avoid extremes of coldness.
- Place information in perspective.

POST – INTERVIEW ASSESSMENT AND DECISION:

More often than not there are more candidates than vacancies. The selectors should assess the suitability of each individual candidate instead of comparing the merits of candidates. It should:

- Systematically assess the evidence obtained in the light of the job requirements.
- In assessing evidence concentrate on solid facts of past behavior as indicators of motivation, attitudes, values, personal qualities and abilities and in sum of potential to do the job. There is a little correlation between the behavior and likely behavior in the actual environment and conditions of work.
- In the assessment process take account of all available evidence. The documents are very useful when written by the authorities competent to confirm the facts of past performance. They are of much more doubtful value when they purport to assess suitability for employment because of the likelihood of bias and the writer's probable lack of direct knowledge of the job requirements.

KEY INTERVIEWER SKILLS:

- LISTENING
- BODY LANGUAGE SENSITIVITY
- COMMUNICATION STYLE
- QUESTIONING

1. **LISTENING:** Most people aren't good listeners. A good listener encourages positive results. We listen best when there is a pay-off or a penalty. Personal listening awareness is the key to constructive change.

2.

3. Four key elements of listening:

a. Focus

- b. Empathy
- c. Emotionalism must be avoided
- d. Feedback

4. **BODY LANGUAGE:** Some common aspects of non – verbal communication (Body Language) include following which can help in knowing what signals you are giving or you can deliberately send the signals you want to.

- **Arm Barriers:** The most common of these is when the arms are folded across the chest, thus protecting the body's vital organs and consequently signifying a defensive action. If the fists are clenched, the person is holding him/herself back (temporarily). A disguised arm fold is when one hand moves across the body unnecessarily to adjust a watchstrap or cuff.
- **Hand to Face Gestures:** A very common hand to face gesture is when the speaker places a finger or fingers in front of the mouth when speaking which is interpreted as an untruth being told when the speaker is rather embarrassed about speaking it. The movement may be traced to an action of wanting to say the words but at the same time, hold them back with the hand. The result is incongruence and rising of suspicion.

If the hand is placed to the cheek, with the forefinger pointing up, often accompanied by a slight tilting of the head, this suggests that the listener is in fact listening and taking account of what is said normally a good sign.

- **Postures:** The 'set' of body whether rigid or relaxed gives immediate signals of reaction and can be accompanied by other non-verbal signals. A forward facing posture with hand obviously placed in the pockets deliberately suggests a power approach.
- **Sitting and Sitting Postures:** How the other person is sitting can give us some good indications of their attitudes. Reversing the chair and sitting, leaning over the back can indicate power and control; slumping (with arms

folded or clasped in the lap) may suggest dejection or submissiveness. The square-on position behind the desk, with the person leaning forward on the desk with the hands placed downwards on the desk and a stern look on the face must signify an aggressive attitude. This is the most consciously noted non-verbal signal.

5. **DIFFERENT TYPES OF QUESTIONING:** The different types of questioning methods are:

- Questions to avoid
 - Open vs. Directive vs. Close ended
 - BEI (Question Cycle Method)
 - Probing
- **Questions to avoid:** Don't ask 'multiple' questions, don't ask 'leading' questions, which give the candidate hints about the kind of answer you want and also don't ask 'no-win' questions. By restricting answers to areas that show the candidate would do something wrong, you won't find what they naturally would do. Think carefully before asking 'clever' questions as an experienced candidate would give impressive answers but if their answers past performance questions don't show their strengths, this type of question is unlikely to reveal them.
- **Open-ended vs. Directive vs. Close-ended Questions:** Open-ended are those that do not define the scope you should take (i.e., how many and what kinds of experiences to discuss). Open-ended questions have more room for creativity. Examples of open-ended questions are: What do you know about our company? , What are your strengths and how do you relate to our company? Or what are your biggest accomplishments; work non-work during the past few years?

Direct Questions are used to gather the data that is factual and objective.

These types of questions do not probe into the values and ideas of the candidate. Examples of direct questions are: With your background, what makes you think you can do this job? Or Are you sure you want this job?

Close-ended Questions are those types of questions which will have answers either yes or no.

- **Behavioral Event Interviewing:** Behavioral based interviews use questions allowing a candidate to tell stories about experiences. The objective is to select and probe for competencies which will result in more effective selection decisions. It includes probing for critical events and specific competencies. Also deciding what data is valid and predicts future success in the job.

The question cycle method is well accepted in the industry today. It includes setting scene questions, asking past performance questions, what-if questions, then more detailed and other questions and lastly giving information about the company and the job.

- **Probing:** The key to getting candidate to talk openly is to ask probing questions. The main purpose of probing is to simultaneously track what the interviewee is saying without direction and constantly following all leads that help reach the objectives of the interview.

4. **CONCLUDING THE INTERVIEW:** Towards the closing of the interview leave time to answer any questions the candidate may have and if appropriate advocate your firm to the candidate. Try to end all interviews on a positive note.

TIPS FOR CONDUCTING SUCCESSFUL INTERVIEWS

Your business' survival depends on hiring the right people. But finding the best employees can be tricky, and if you don't have the right interviewing skills, you risk losing a brilliant candidate — or worse — hiring a person that's not qualified for the job. And in a competitive job market, conducting effective interviews is more important than ever. While you're sizing up a candidate, that person is also considering you as a potential employer. Here are some tips to help you effectively screen the candidate, make a good impression and ensure that the candidate gets the information they need about the job and your company.

- **Understand the purpose of the interview.** Hiring the right person is the goal of [interviewing](#), but not necessarily the purpose of an interview. An interview is your chance to collect information about the candidate sitting in front of you. It's your opportunity to find out if the applicant is qualified for a particular job, if they are truly interested in the available position and if they fit your company's culture.
- **Rethink your interviewing strategy.** General questions like "Where do you see yourself in five years?" won't tell you much about the candidate sitting in front of you. That inquiry and many other standard [interview questions](#) sidestep what you really need to know - how the person will perform in a specific role. To find and hire smart employees you have to adopt smart interviewing tactics that uncover a candidate's abilities, talents, strengths and weaknesses.
- **Develop a list of desired skills.** You can't formulate insightful questions until you know what skills to look for.

- **Create a list of interview questions.** After you develop a list of skills, put together a list of interview questions that will help you [learn](#) more about the candidate. Construct open-ended questions that invite candidates to share information and talk about their experiences. Today, many interviewers use behavior-based questions to discover how a person handled a situation in the past and to determine how they'll react to a similar situation in the future. Try posing questions such as "Tell me about a time that you missed a project deadline. What happened and how did you manage the problem?"
- **Check your list twice.** Review your list of interview questions. You should have a good mix of opinion-based, credential-based, experience-based and behavior-based questions that will provide a complete view of the candidate's background and personality.
- **Tell the applicant about the interview format.** After you introduce yourself, put the candidate at ease by telling them the basic structure of the interview. You want them to relax, speak freely and provide detailed answers to your inquiries.
- **Prepare for questions.** Make sure you have adequate information about the company to answer a candidate's questions. They may ask about your business' core functions, number of employees, future plans, culture or a variety of other things. Bring a [media](#) kit to the interview, or prepare a fact sheet that lists relevant company data and history.
- **Take notes.** [Interviewing](#) requires superb listening skills, but listening isn't enough. Capture the details of the interview on paper to jog your memory, noting key actions and outcomes. Taking objective notes and recording responses will help you compare candidates when it's time to make a hiring decision.

EVALUATION AND SELECTION:

Continual monitoring of your recruiting process will lead to better hires. When you identify an issue in your process, adjust your programs accordingly. In addition to tracking traditional metrics such as time-to-fill and cost-per-hire, make sure you take into account ways to measure some of the intangible metrics, such as quality of hire and retention. Keeping track of your recruiting and retention successes and challenges will help you fine tune your program into an effective and efficient hiring system that your whole company can embrace.

Evaluation requires a total comprehension of the job and of the candidate and of their relationship to each other. A very important concept that the recruiter should be aware of at the time of evaluation and selection is that of “Bad Recruitment.” While doing a recruitment it should always be kept in mind that it does not turn out to be a bad recruitment.

Bad Recruitment

The entire effort, time, cost and resources that are spent in the recruitment process, go wasted if the recruitment turns out to be a “bad recruitment.” A bad recruitment is one where the hired candidate is not able to do justice to the role/job assigned to him/leaves the organization very soon/the cost of recruitment is higher than the value addition that the new employee is expected to do in the organization etc. In such a scenario the entire purpose of recruitment is defeated, hence at the time of recruiting the HR manager should all the time have at the back of his mind that his recruitment should not turn out to be a bad recruitment.

Bad recruitment occurs in 3 situations:

- **Cannot do:** The person lacks the skills required.
- **Will not do:** The person lacks attitude.
- **Does not know what to do:** The person lacks the knowledge.

Cost of Bad Recruitment

1. Direct Recruitment Costs

- ❑ Advertising
- ❑ Travel and stay
- ❑ Time costs of people concerned

2. Induction Costs

- ❑ Administrative costs
- ❑ Relocation costs

3. Stabilization Costs

- ❑ Learning time
- ❑ Mentoring and Team time

4. De – Motivation Costs

- ❑ Unproductive time
- ❑ Other people leaving
- ❑ Team loss

5. Client Related

- Internal/External Client loss
- Future business loss

6. Leaving Costs

- Other people leaving
- Redundancy costs
- Handover costs

Why Bad Recruitment Occurs?

Recruitment has acquired immense importance in today's organizations. Organizations have realized the Value of human capital and its role in their development. Recruitment is the first step in the process of acquiring and retaining human resources for an organization. In today's rapidly changing business environment organizations have to respond quickly to requirements for people

- Poor analysis of job function.
- Poor analysis of necessary personality – skill profile
- Inadequate initial screening
- Inadequate interviewing techniques
- Inadequate questioning techniques

- Poor utilization of second opinions
- References were not checked
- Other issues like Halo Effect, Stereotyping, Similar-to-me Effect, First Impression, and Leniency Errors, etc should also be evaluated.

CHAPTER 3

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The second chapter discusses methodology. Then the collection of secondary and primary data is presented.

2.1 SAMPLING: Random Sample-50 Expatriates

2.3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The choice of methodology greatly depends on the research purpose and research questions. Choosing a proper methodology is important to achieve the aim of the dissertation, to get valid and reliable results. The research is undertaken through an Exploratory research cum analytical design.

2.4 RESEARCH APPROACH

An analytical approach is used in the dissertation. First, the existing theories about the expatriate managers' training, and some related culture theories were critically reviewed. Secondly, several hypotheses were developed and analysis was done accordingly

2.5 DATA COLLECTION

The research is undertaken through an Exploratory research cum analytical design. The study uses both primary research tools & secondary research tools.

Primary research was carried out with the help of a questionnaire, which aimed to understand the perception of expatriate managers.

Journals, books, internet, research papers, etc were used as sources of secondary research.

1) Primary Data

A detailed self-administered questionnaire was used.

Type of questionnaire: Structured and Undisguised

STRUCTURED AND UNDISGUISED QUESTIONNAIRE

For this project a structured questionnaire is used where each question specify the set of responses alternatives and the response format. A structured questionnaire can be of three types multiple choices, dichotomous or a scale. The questionnaire used here is undisguised, as the respondents clearly know the purpose of this survey and intentions behind it.

2) Secondary Data

Our sources for secondary data were mainly books, the internet and articles. There are many researches done in the field of expatriates. Nevertheless, a complex literature review was conducted to learn more about training methodologies of expatriates.

CHAPTER 4

RESEARCH ANALYSIS & GRAPHICAL DATA INTERPRETATION

RECRUITMENT PROCESS

DETERMINING MANPOWER REQUIREMENT

A Recruitment analysis is conducted depending on the job profile. A well- designed and comprehensive recruitment analysis is invaluable to an organization's well being. Recruitment analysis basically ensures the availability of the right resources in the right place to match the future organizational needs. Recruitment analysis

can be defined as the process of ensuring the right number of qualified people, into the right job at the right time to deliver the results in an efficient and effective manner. Recruitment is the process of searching for and attracting qualified candidates to apply for the positions that are available. Whether your company is heavily recruiting or in the midst of a hiring freeze, you should always have a recruiting plan. Plans will vary based on hiring volume and type of position, but you should articulate a standard strategy of how you recruit and fill positions. A well-

defined recruiting strategy will help ensure that the right employees are in place when needed.

The objectives are:

5. To maintain the required quantity and quality of human resources required.
6. To forecast the turnover/attrition rates.
7. To plan to meet organizational human resource needs at the time of expansion or diversification.
8. To make contingent plans to handle sudden requirements and situations of shortfall.

SOURCING RESUMES:

There various methods of recruiting are given below:

3. **INTERNAL SOURCES:** Many organizations try and identify employees from within the organization to be groomed to take on higher responsibilities. Internal recruiting is beneficial, as workers know the firm culture; managers already know the workers and the internal advancement can motivate the employees. In today's technologically advanced world many organizations depend on their HRIS. Some of the internal sources are:

- e. **Job Postings:** Openings are published on bulletin boards (electronic or hard copy) or in lists available to all employees. Interested employees must reply within a specified number of days and they may or may not have to obtain the consent of their immediate supervisors. This is the process used by managers to provide information about job openings to employees.
- f. **Employee Referrals:** Employees working with an organization recommend their friends or acquaintances for vacant positions in the organization. This source is usually one of the most effective

and reliable methods of recruiting because many qualified people especially for the lower and middle management are reached at a very low cost to the company.

- g. **Contract Management:** Temporary worker pools are created to meet out the unexpected demand of the human resource in the organization.
- h. **Previous Employees:** Organizations can recruit their previous employees as they can prove to be reliable as they already know about the organization policies and procedures and need not to be trained and easily adjust to the environment.

4. EXTERNAL SOURCES: To meet demands for talent brought about by business growth to seek fresh ideas or to replace employees who leave organizations periodically turn to the outside labor market. Managers look outside the firm for people who have not worked at the firm before. The following methods are adopted to recruit people form outside:

- g. **Press Advertisements:** Advertisements are placed in both newspapers and trade journals and three factors influence the choice of this media-cost, profile of the readership and circulation. Some factors affecting the design of advertising are:
 - The image of the organization.
 - The nature of the job.
 - The chosen media.
 - The prediction of the target market.

-
- h. **Walk-INS:** In a walk-in no prior appointment is there, the applicant approaches the organization directly. It is the most common and least expensive approach as in this the job seekers submit unsolicited application letters or resumes and from employees point of view, walk-ins are preferable as they are free from the hassles associated with other methods of recruitment. Direct applications are particularly effective in filling entry-level and unskilled vacancies, some organizations compile pools of potential employees from direct applications for skilled positions.
 - i. **Employment Agencies:** Employment agencies now provide occupations for almost all levels in an organization. They are broadly classified into public or state agencies, private agencies and headhunters.
 - j. **Job Sites:** Various job sites like Naukri.com, Times jobs.com, Monster.com etc come in very handy in finding candidates with the desired skills.
 - k. **Job fairs** - Job fairs typically work best for entry-level candidates, but events targeting diversity and/or specialty careers, e.g. engineers, can be found.
 - l. **Corporate Web site** - When job seekers are interested in a company they will go directly to that company's Web site to conduct research and/or look for available jobs. Make sure your Web site's job section makes it easy to find and apply for jobs.

SHORT – LISTING:

Short listing is the transition phase between recruitment and selection. It is the stage where the total number of applicants is reduced to select the group the employer wishes to carry on to the selection phase. Short listing may comprise of several stages depending on the number of application received, the complexity of the job requirements and sophistication of the selection process used by the organization. Short listing comprises of:

4. **KNOWLEDGE OF MATCHING CV's:** First of all the candidates are short listed on the basis of matching the CV's. The CV's or curriculum vitae are universally used and their form is standardized.

Typically a CV comprises of:

- Evidence of Skills, Abilities and Achievements
- Employment History
- Experience
- Education
- Languages

5. **METHODS OF SHORT LISTING:** The most common way to reduce the number of applications by short-listing them by categorizing them to various departments first. Then asking the department heads to shortlist the appropriate candidates accordingly.

6. SHORT-LISTING – THE PROCESS:

- Short listing must be carried out independently by at least two people and ideally, as many of the interview panel as possible.
- Any member of staff, who may prejudice the outcome, should be excluded from short listing.
- Short listing should always be carried out using the person specification so that applications can be measured and assessed against criteria and be made on the basis of fact and not assumptions.
- The use of short-listing form is recommended. The short-listing panel to record individual assessment of each candidate and provide feedback can use short-listing form.
- Short-listing form must be used at the interview stage. Short-listing decisions must be based only on the information contained in the application form and any other supporting information supplied by the candidate. Irrelevant information in the application form should be disregarded.
- The attributes in the person specification must be consistently applied to all candidates irrespective of their gender, ethnic origin, age, socio-economic background, disability, religious or political beliefs, family circumstances, sexual orientation or other irrelevant factors.
- Some information can only be determined at interview stage or as group exercises, presentation, tests, etc.
- After individual assessment of each application, decision of whom to short list must be taken.

Once a short list has been drawn up, candidates should be invited for interview.

In the short listing of candidates the following things should be kept in mind:

- Evidence of skills, abilities and achievements that match the criteria that have been specified as essential for the job as closely as possible.
- Consistency of employment (look for unexplained gaps).
- Qualifications compatible with the dates given.
- Evidence of career development.
- Evidence of industry knowledge.
- Previous employer.

FILTERING:

Filtering techniques are used to reduce the number of applicants and also gather relevant information needed before conducting the interview. Filtering techniques involve different methods, such as:

- Knowledge Based Filtering
- Skill Based Filtering
- Attitudinal/Behavioral Filtering

- **KNOWLEDGE BASED FILTERING:** This method is used when the number of applications is more like in Campus recruitment. The evaluation is done based on candidate's academic qualification, percentage of marks scored and experience level or through simple written tests.

SKILL BASED FILTERING: The tasks and skills that may be assessed using simulation exercises are varied. Different types of simulation exercise include:

- **In-trays:** In-trays or in-baskets involve working from the contents of a manager's in-tray, which typically consist of letters, memos and background information. You may be asked to deal with paperwork and make decisions, balancing the volume of work against a tight schedule.
- **Test of productive thinking:** The tests look at the volume, diversity and originality of your ideas. You are presented with open-ended questions relating to various problems and situations and are asked to generate responses within a time limit.
- **Group exercises:** Group exercises are timed discussions, where a group of participants work together to tackle a work-related problem. Sometimes you are given a particular role within a team, for example the sales manager or personnel manager. There would be assessors, who are not looking for right or wrong answers, but for how you interact with your colleagues within the team.
- **Presentation:** You may be asked to make a formal presentation to a number of assessors either on a topic given in advance or in some cases to interpret and analyze given information and present a case to support a decision.
- **Fact-Finding Exercises:** In a fact-finding exercise, you may be asked to reach a destination starting from only a partial knowledge. Your task is to decide what additional information you need to make the decision and sometimes also to question the assessor to obtain this information.
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- When interview boards are held, discuss and agree the objectives, criteria, the coverage plan and the areas that each board member will cover.

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- Begin with introduction and a brief explanation of the purpose and scope of the interview.
- Follow the broad chronological, systematic coverage plan throughout in order to ensure a comprehensive coverage. Deviations are likely to create gaps in the information obtained.

- In board interviews arrange for each interviewer to interview in turn.
- Pay utmost attention to the form of question, i.e.:
 - Concentrate on acquiring as much evidence as possible of potential ability to do the required job, based on the facts of past behavior and achievements.
 - In general avoid hypothetical questions, especially those which have no bearing on the job. They can only produce hypothetical answers.
 - Use a simple open question form which does not imply answers.
- Be constantly alert to possible effects of the interviewee's non-verbal behavior and manner and possibility of misinterpretation of intentions by candidates. Be a little sympathetic and avoid extremes of coldness.
- Place information in perspective.

POST – INTERVIEW ASSESSMENT AND DECISION:

More often than not there are more candidates than vacancies. The selectors should assess the suitability of each individual candidate instead of comparing the merits of candidates. It should:

- Systematically assess the evidence obtained in the light of the job requirements.
- In assessing evidence concentrate on solid facts of past behavior as indicators of motivation, attitudes, values, personal qualities and abilities and in sum of potential to do the job. There is a little correlation between the behavior and likely behavior in the actual environment and conditions of work.

- In the assessment process take account of all available evidence. The documents are very useful when written by the authorities competent to confirm the facts of past performance. They are of much more doubtful value when they purport to assess suitability for employment because of the likelihood of bias and the writer's probable lack of direct knowledge of the job requirements.

KEY INTERVIEWER SKILLS:

- **LISTENING**
- **BODY LANGUAGE SENSITIVITY**
- **COMMUNICATION STYLE**
- **QUESTIONING**

6. **LISTENING:** Most people aren't good listeners. A good listener encourages positive results. We listen best when there is a pay-off or a penalty. Personal listening awareness is the key to constructive change. It should be kept in mind that work and listening are inseparable and lazy listening is hidden cost in business. We tend to equate "listening" with "hearing" and that is simply not the case. Good listening implies heightened awareness of what you hear, accurate reception of the information presented to you and integration of information in such a way that it is useful.

Four key elements of listening:

- a. Focus
- b. Empathy
- c. Emotionalism must be avoided
- d. Feedback

7. **BODY LANGUAGE:** Some common aspects of non – verbal communication (Body Language) include following which can help in knowing what signals you are giving or you can deliberately send the signals you want to.

- **Arm Barriers:** The most common of these is when the arms are folded across the chest, thus protecting the body's vital organs and consequently signifying a defensive action. If the fists are clenched, the person is holding him/herself back (temporarily). A disguised arm fold is when one hand moves across the body unnecessarily to adjust a watchstrap or cuff.

- **Hand to Face Gestures:** A very common hand to face gesture is when the speaker places a finger or fingers in front of the mouth when speaking which is interpreted as an untruth being told when the speaker is rather embarrassed about speaking it. The movement may be traced to an action of wanting to say the words but at the same time, hold them back with the hand. The result is incongruence and rising of suspicion.

If the hand is placed to the cheek, with the forefinger pointing up, often accompanied by a slight tilting of the head, this suggests that the listener is in fact listening and taking account of what is said normally a good sign.

- **Postures:** The 'set' of body whether rigid or relaxed gives immediate signals of reaction and can be accompanied by other non-verbal signals. A forward facing posture with hand obviously placed in the pockets deliberately suggests a power approach.

- **Sitting and Sitting Postures:** How the other person is sitting can give us some good indications of their attitudes. Reversing the chair and sitting, leaning over the back can indicate power and control; slumping (with arms folded or clasped in the lap) may suggest dejection or submissiveness. The square-on position behind the desk, with the person leaning forward on the desk with the hands placed downwards on the desk and a stern look on the face must signify an aggressive attitude. This is the most consciously noted non-verbal signal.

8. **DIFFERENT TYPES OF QUESTIONING:** The different types of questioning methods are:

- Questions to avoid
 - Open vs. Directive vs. Close ended
 - BEI (Question Cycle Method)
 - Probing
- **Questions to avoid:** Don't ask 'multiple' questions, don't ask 'leading' questions, which give the candidate hints about the kind of answer you want and also don't ask 'no-win' questions. By restricting answers to areas that show the candidate would do something wrong, you won't find what they naturally would do. Think carefully before asking 'clever' questions as an experienced candidate would give impressive answers but if their answers past performance questions don't show their strengths, this type of question is unlikely to reveal them.
- **Open-ended vs. Directive vs. Close-ended Questions:** Open-ended are those that do not define the scope you should take (i.e., how many and what kinds of experiences to discuss). Open-ended questions have more room for creativity. Examples of open-ended questions are: What do you know about our company? , What are your strengths and how do you relate to our company? Or what are your biggest accomplishments; work non-work during the past few years?

Direct Questions are used to gather the data that is factual and objective. These types of questions do not probe into the values and ideas of the candidate. Examples of direct questions are: With your background, what makes you think you can do this job? Or Are you sure you want this job?

Close-ended Questions are those types of questions which will have answers either yes or no.

- **Behavioral Event Interviewing:** Behavioral based interviews use questions allowing a candidate to tell stories about experiences. The objective is to select and probe for competencies which will result in more effective selection decisions. It includes probing for critical events and specific competencies. Also deciding what data is valid and predicts future success in the job.

The question cycle method is well accepted in the industry today. It includes setting scene questions, asking past performance questions, what-if questions, then more detailed and other questions and lastly giving information about the company and the job.

- **Probing:** The key to getting candidate to talk openly is to ask probing questions. The main purpose of probing is to simultaneously track what the interviewee is saying without direction and constantly following all leads that help reach the objectives of the interview.

4. **CONCLUDING THE INTERVIEW:** Towards the closing of the interview leave time to answer any questions the candidate may have and if appropriate advocate your firm to the candidate. Try to end all interviews on a positive note.

TIPS FOR CONDUCTING SUCCESSFUL INTERVIEWS

Your business' survival depends on hiring the right people. But finding the best employees can be tricky, and if you don't have the right interviewing skills, you risk losing a brilliant candidate — or worse — hiring a person that's not qualified for the job. And in a competitive job market, conducting effective interviews is more important than ever. While you're sizing up a candidate, that person is also considering you as a potential employer. Here are some tips to help you effectively screen the candidate, make a good impression and ensure that the candidate gets the information they need about the job and your company.

- **Understand the purpose of the interview.** Hiring the right person is the goal of [interviewing](#), but not necessarily the purpose of an interview. An interview is your chance to collect information about the candidate sitting in front of you. It's your opportunity to find out if the applicant is qualified for a particular job, if they are truly interested in the available position and if they fit your company's culture.
- **Rethink your interviewing strategy.** General questions like "Where do you see yourself in five years?" won't tell you much about the candidate sitting in front of you. That inquiry and many other standard [interview questions](#) sidestep what you really need to know - how the person will perform in a specific role. To find and hire smart employees you have to adopt smart interviewing tactics that uncover a candidate's abilities, talents, strengths and weaknesses.
- **Develop a list of desired skills.** You can't formulate insightful questions until you know what skills to look for.
- **Create a list of interview questions.** After you develop a list of skills, put together a list of interview questions that will help you [learn](#) more about the

candidate. Construct open-ended questions that invite candidates to share information and talk about their experiences. Today, many interviewers use behavior-based questions to discover how a person handled a situation in the past and to determine how they'll react to a similar situation in the future. Try posing questions such as "Tell me about a time that you missed a project deadline. What happened and how did you manage the problem?"

- **Check your list twice.** Review your list of interview questions. You should have a good mix of opinion-based, credential-based, experience-based and behavior-based questions that will provide a complete view of the candidate's background and personality.
- **Tell the applicant about the interview format.** After you introduce yourself, put the candidate at ease by telling them the basic structure of the interview. You want them to relax, speak freely and provide detailed answers to your inquiries.
- **Prepare for questions.** Make sure you have adequate information about the company to answer a candidate's questions. They may ask about your business' core functions, number of employees, future plans, culture or a variety of other things. Bring a [media](#) kit to the interview, or prepare a fact sheet that lists relevant company data and history.
- **Take notes.** [Interviewing](#) requires superb listening skills, but listening isn't enough. Capture the details of the interview on paper to jog your memory, noting key actions and outcomes. Taking objective notes and recording responses will help you compare candidates when it's time to make a hiring decision.

EVALUATION AND SELECTION:

Continual monitoring of your recruiting process will lead to better hires. When you identify an issue in your process, adjust your programs accordingly. In addition to tracking traditional metrics such as time-to-fill and cost-per-hire, make sure you take into account ways to measure some of the intangible metrics, such as quality of hire and retention. Keeping track of your recruiting and retention successes and challenges will help you fine tune your program into an effective and efficient hiring system that your whole company can embrace.

Evaluation requires a total comprehension of the job and of the candidate and of their relationship to each other. A very important concept that the recruiter should be aware of at the time of evaluation and selection is that of “Bad Recruitment.” While doing a recruitment it should always be kept in mind that it does not turn out to be a bad recruitment.

Bad Recruitment

The entire effort, time, cost and resources that are spent in the recruitment process, go wasted if the recruitment turns out to be a “bad recruitment.” A bad recruitment is one where the hired candidate is not able to do justice to the role/job assigned to him/leaves the organization very soon/the cost of recruitment is higher than the value addition that the new employee is expected to do in the organization etc. In such a scenario the entire purpose of recruitment is defeated, hence at the time of recruiting the HR manager should all the time have at the back of his mind that his recruitment should not turn out to be a bad recruitment.

Bad recruitment occurs in 3 situations:

- **Cannot do:** The person lacks the skills required.
- **Will not do:** The person lacks attitude.
- **Does not know what to do:** The person lacks the knowledge.

Cost of Bad Recruitment

4. Direct Recruitment Costs

- Advertising
- Travel and stay
- Time costs of people concerned

5. Induction Costs

- Administrative costs
- Relocation costs

6. Stabilization Costs

- Learning time
- Mentoring and Team time

4. De – Motivation Costs

- Unproductive time
- Other people leaving
- Team loss

5. Client Related

- ❑ Internal/External Client loss
- ❑ Future business loss

6. Leaving Costs

- ❑ Other people leaving
- ❑ Redundancy costs
- ❑ Handover costs

Why Bad Recruitment Occurs?

Recruitment has acquired immense importance in today's organizations. Organizations have realized the Value of human capital and its role in their development. Recruitment is the first step in the process of acquiring and retaining human resources for an organization. In today's rapidly changing business environment organizations have to respond quickly to requirements for people.

Bad recruitments affect the company and the individual. The wrong person doing the wrong job is harmful to the companies. Yet in all cases, the cause of the bad recruitment can be traced to one of the following reasons:

- Poor analysis of job function.
- Poor analysis of necessary personality – skill profile
- Inadequate initial screening
- Inadequate interviewing techniques
- Inadequate questioning techniques
- Poor utilization of second opinions
- References were not checked
- Other issues like Halo Effect, Stereotyping, Similar-to-me Effect, First Impression, and Leniency Errors, etc should also be evaluated.

RECRUITMENT PROCEDURE

Step9.The first round of interview is conducted by a panel comprising of 2-3 members, this is mainly the technical round where the candidates overall knowledge and expertise are judged.

Step10.After a thorough technical screening, the candidates are interviewed by the Director operations [D(O)], he interviews them and decides the candidates overall suitability in the organization. In DABUR no permanent recruitment takes place without an interview with the D(O).

Step11.Once the candidate is recommended by the D(O), there is an HR round where the salary of the candidate is negotiated. This is done by the HR office, New Delhi

Step12.After the salary negotiation, the New Delhi Office sends the candidate details to the Corporate Office Gaziabad for reference check and for generation of appointment letters.

Step13.The Corporate Office Mumbai, after conducting a reference check generates appointment letters and dispatches the same.

Step14.The selected candidates are expected to join the organization within 15days of receiving the appointment letter. They are required to undergo a complete medical check-up before joining DABUR and submit a copy of the same at the time of joining.

Step15.Retention and Updating of the Records.

RETENTION OF RECORDS:

- All records of selection processes of hired candidates are retained in his/her personnel file.
- All records of selection processes of rejected candidates are also retained for a period of one year from the day on which the candidate's last recruitment process was held.
- These records are cleared at the end of one year after scrutiny.

UPDATING OF RECORDS:

- The detail of every employee who has been hired has to be updated within five working days of the date on which his appointment letter has been issued.
- If the new hire fails to turn up on his/her first working day, this is added to his records within three working days from the date on which he was supposed to report to work for the first time.
- The details of the employees who have finally joined Dabur has to be to company Database on the same working day when s/he first reports to work all these records are saved in a particular format.

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HUMAN RESOURCE INFORMATION SYSTEM (HRIS)

Human Resource Information System or Human Resource Management Systems (HRMS) shapes an intersection between Human resource management (HRM) and [information technology](#). It merges HRM as a discipline and in particular it's basic HR activities and processes with the information technology field. It is a systematic procedure for collecting, storing, maintaining and validating data needed by an organization about its human resources, personnel activities, and organization unit characteristics.

HRIS is a fast growing area of HR due to the technology driven culture we live in. HRIS are software systems that are designed to make the process of HR record keeping much more effective and efficient. The systems are created to hold employee information, and they can span from just payroll systems to broad relational databases that hold a variety of employment information. A key benefit to computerized records is the ability to run reports and connect data. In a company without a formal HRIS system, you'll find HR professionals utilizing Access, Excel, or manual filing systems to track and maintain the needed information concerning employees.

Traditionally, human resources departments relied on multiple programs in each department. An HRIS integrates all of these programs through a common database and single-user interface. An HRIS combines separate HR systems into a centralized database that performs the majority of HR transactions.

ROLE OF HUMAN RESOURCE INFORMATION SYSTEM

HRIS is a much more dynamic concept than the traditional personnel function in an organization which has multiple functions since it not only does it deal with the problems of administering the personnel functions but also helps the organization in several ways as under:

1. Providing support to other systems – Supportive Role
2. Development of systems and research – Administrative role
3. Management of Human Resources – Managerial Role
4. Developing Competencies of various kinds – Developmental Role
5. Catering the process needs – Process Role

Objectives of HRIS :

1. To offer an adequate, comprehensive and on-going information system about people and jobs in a centralized and accessible location.
2. To supply up to date information at a reasonable cost.
3. To deliver an accurate, timely management information.
4. To allow an easy and faster access to data and to facilitate human resource planning decisions.
5. To provide data security.

HRIS is designed to monitor, control the movement of people from the time they join the organization till the time they decide to leave the organization. It actually provides the support for the following sub systems:

1. Recruitment Information
2. Leave, transfer, promotion, increment Information
3. Manpower planning Information
4. Training Information
5. Performance appraisal Information
6. Payroll Information

Components of an HRIS

An HRIS is a system with 6 basic components:

1. Database
2. Data Entry/Input
3. Data Maintenance
4. Information Retrieval
5. Human Resource Information Center
6. Output

DATABASE

Database is one of the major components of an HRIS. It refers to the centralized system which stores, manages and maintains the information related o various elements such as maintaining the employee profile, keeping the track of all human resource related activities or maintaining the record of day to day activities to facilitate the transfer access to data, integration of data.

INPUT

The input function enters the personnel information into the HRIS. In the past data entry was often the only way. Today, scanning technology allows computers to scan and store the actual image of an original document, including signatures and handwritten notes.

DATA MAINTENANCE

After the data has been entered into the information system, the data maintenance function updates and adds the new data to the database. In the traditional way of data entry and maintenance, clerks do this manually; they file paper documents and make the appropriate entries in the files. Computerized systems accomplish this function accurately and rapidly, often making the new data available only seconds after being input. This area is going rapidly to allow for electronic storage and workflow management.

INFORMATION RETRIEVAL

One of the most important uses of the centralized system of HRIS is the faster access to the information. An information system always helps in an accurate and the faster retrieval of the information as desired by the user. The information stored can be retrieved at any point of time as and when need arises.

HUMAN RESOURCE INFORMATION CENTER

Human Resource Information Center (HRIC) refers to the staff responsible for day – to –day activities of the HRIS and who are subject matter experts. Following is the list of functional duties performed by HRIC team during the implementation of Human Resource Information System:

- Preparing data for entry into the system
- Editing the data

- Handling request for information
- Distribution of output to users
- Developing the specification for system change
- Integrity of data elements
- HRIS routine data administration, etc

OUTPUT

The most valuable function of HRIS is the output generated. To generate valuable output for computers users, HRIS must process that output, make necessary calculations, and then format the presentation in a way that users can understand.

Need for HRIS

With the rapid advances in Information Technology, a tighter labor market with higher recruitment and retention efforts by employers together with an increasing mobile workforce in a global market place, the face of the Human Resource function has changed forever. All these influences represent both challenges and opportunities for all management functions and especially for Human Resources, with employees' skills and knowledge becoming the key factor to success in today's very competitive marketplace.

In today's business environment, the HR functions must not only be focused on the work place but also the market place and linked directly to the core business strategy. In order to achieve this, the HR department should be an integrated unit within the business and therefore centralized.

Need For Change

There are several very important reasons for regularly reviewing your current system with what is available in the software marketplace. First and foremost: cash

the bottom line. When was the last time anyone in your company had taken a hard look at the costs associated with your current HR software? How much time is spent maintaining personnel records, recording time, running and correcting payrolls, maintaining training and succession files, etc? How much money and resources are being used to pull information from multiple databases or converting data in order to run reports? How many double and triple entries are being made just to preserve the integrity of multiple systems and databases? These are just a few questions that probably aren't being asked or answered.

A company could attain cost savings if timely information was available throughout the organization. A real time integrated HR system could help you spot costly negative cash flows such as high-targeted turnover, high levels of absenteeism within certain business units, and low retention. Company-wide reporting through an integrated HRIS system can enable managers to proactively adjust policy to avoid these unwanted expenses. Tracking and managing employees training and development on a single system allows the company to internally promote and fill vacancies internally, further reducing recruitment expenses. By integrating external recruitment, position requirements can be matched with applicant's qualifications, also reducing costs through decreased turnover. Downloading payroll results and other cash flows out of payroll into accounting can be automatic through an integrated system. This only a brief review of cost savings that can be achieved though an integrated HR system.

Selection Process

Selecting HRIS software can appear to be a relatively ambiguous process to decision makers as the information is always favorably skewed from software vendors .By taking a few steps before interviewing vendors, you can accurately obtain company-specific information. Before choosing HRIS the following points must be considered by the company.

Benefits

- How will our organization benefit from a new HRIS system?
- What are the risks associated with implementing new HRIS software?
- What are the risks associated with deciding to continue to operate as before?

Financial Aspects

- How much value will this software add to our organization and what are potential savings?
- How do the newly gained benefits compare to the overall investment?
- What are the risks associated with deciding to continue to operate as before?
- How much money is being wasted on opportunity costs associated with the current HR software?

Track Records

- Which and how many other companies within our industry use this software? What is their satisfaction level?
- How experienced are the consulting firms in the industry?

Internal Resources

- How resistant are users to change?
- How can I form a dedicated project team?
- How long will it take for users to be self-sufficient?

The Future

- Which and how many other companies within our industry use this software? What is their satisfaction level?
- How much value will this software add to our organization and what are potential savings?
- How do the newly gained benefits compare to the overall investment?
- What are the risks associated with the deciding to continue to operate as before?
- How much money is being wasted on opportunity costs associated with the current HR software?

There is always some degree of uncertainty when it comes to selecting a provider for your HRIS system, but there are ways to reduce this uncertainty. By identifying specific needs of a new system, understanding the barriers to making the best decision and taking measures to overcome these barriers, your company can better understand the process and reduce this uncertainty.

HRIS Practices AT DABUR

At DABUR, a very traditional approach of maintaining HRIS is followed. The organization does not make use of any special software for this purpose. DABUR uses Microsoft-excel for maintaining all its HRIS, and at present does not have any centralized information system in the organization.

The HR department circulates Role Summary Sheets/Performance Appraisal forms to all the employees of the organization, irrespective of their project and cadre. Role Summary sheets are circulated once in every six months whereas the

Appraisal is done only once a year. These sheets are filled by the employees of all departments and sent back to the HR, for updating its HRIS.

PROBLEMS IN THE CURRENT SYSTEM

The current practice of maintaining employee records in excel has the following disadvantages:

1. Lack of proper workflow in the organization
2. Data Inaccuracy
3. Improper handling of the information
4. Traditional way of generating the reports
5. Longer time to retrieve data
6. The entire process of circulating Role Summary Sheets/Performance Appraisal Form in all departments, collecting them; in itself takes very long. The entire exercise takes almost a month and within this duration there are fresh joinings, resignations and transfers. Hence the data is not very reliable.

IN THE RECRUITMENT PROCESS

- My role included downloading profiles from Naukri.com and initial screening of the CV's.
- Then getting these profiles short listed from the concerned head of the department.
- Lining up short listed candidates for all levels of interview i.e., for the first, second and the final round.
- Coordinating interviews with the panelist as well as the candidates with regards to the timing, date and place of the interview.
- Preparing detailed Synopsis before the interview for the consultation of the interviewer panelists.
- Preparing MIS of the selected candidates to be sent for approval to Corporate Office, Gaziabad.
- Also preparing MIS format of the selected candidates to be sent to the VP-HR.
- As soon as the approval is sent by the Gaziabad Office, communicating to the candidates to send their current organization's appointment letter and salary slip for further processing.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

CONCLUSION

This summer Project has given me immense exposure to learn about different HR functions of a large company. I have learnt a lot and experienced what is the recent HR scenario of HRD in a large company. For this project I took help of the books and internet that gives me a good knowledge about different HR functions and policies.

LIMITATIONS

HRM is an affair for the management. It needs a handsome amount and longtime. So management has to play safe game for the benefits of the company as well as the workers. One wrong decision may enforce the company to fall into deep troubles. So selecting the weak areas of staffs and workers should be done every carefully. For that the management should be conduct a test.

For providing an effective HR functions, company requires a knowledgeable management. Selecting a particular manager is again a difficult job. Trainer demands handsome money. Training needs time and cost both.

To conclude, it is very clear that training should be provided but not at the loss of the company. It is very costly and time taking affair. But it is more important for the development of the company. So management can't avoid it any cost.

ANALYSIS

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GRAPHICAL DATA INTERPRETATION

It is the last stage of survey. Through good presentation, significant facts and comparisons are highlighted. **The presentation of facts done by preparing charts like bar charts, pie charts etc.**

The following interpretation has been done on the basis of the questionnaires filled up the recruiters of Dabur India Ltd., Ghaziabad (U.P.). The main aim behind this interpretation is to show how effectively recruitment is done by the recruiters of Dabur India Ltd., Ghaziabad (U.P.) and their opinions regarding the recruitment process

1. ARE JOB PORTALS BEST SOURCE OF FINDING THE CANDIDATES?

Particulars	Respondents	%
Yes	11	12
No	5	33
Others:References	7	11
Internal Database	11	10
Total	30	100

2. MINIMUM NUMBER OF CALLS MADE TO THE CANDIDATES IN ONE WEEK :

Particulars	No. of respondents	%
Less than 15	4	13.3
Between 15-20	17	56.7
More than 20	9	30%
Total	30	100

3) PERCENTAGE OF RESUMES FORWARDED FOR FORMATTING PURPOSES:

Particulars	No. of respondents	%
5	20	66.6
5-10	8	26.7
Above 10	2	6.7
Total	30	100

4. DURATION OF THE CALL PROCEDURE:

Particulars	No. of respondents	%
15 minutes	6	26
Between 15-20 minutes	21	61
More than 20 minutes	3	13
Total	30	100

5. PERCENTAGE OF CANDIDATES SELECTED BY THE ARTECH'S CLIENTS at DABUR INDIA LTD.

Particulars	No. of respondents	%
Below 40%	3	10
40-80%	10	33
above 80%	17	57
Total	30	100

6. PERCENTAGE OF BIO-DATA REJECTED :

Particulars	No. of respondents	%
20%	6	20
20-50%	15	50
Above 50%	9	30
Total	30	100

7. MINIMUM % OF CANDIDATES SELECTED IN THE TELEPHONIC ROUND WITHIN 1 MONTH AT DABUR INDIA LTD.:

Particulars	No. of respondents	%
Below 20%	5	16.7
20-50%	15	50
50-70%	10	33.3
Above 70%	0	0
Total	30	100

8. IS TELEPHONIC INTERVIEW SUFFICIENT TO JUDGE THE OVERALL CAPABILITIES OF A CANDIDATE:

Particulars	No. of respondents	%
Yes	12	40
No	18	60
Total	30	100

CHAPTER 5

RESEARCH FINDINGS

COMMON MISTAKES MADE BY RECRUITERS:

- Recruiters do not spend enough time talking to the candidates. They must probe a candidate on the following points:
 - Resume-project wise.
 - Availability, willingness & commitment.
 - Whether they have any offers in hand.
 - Whether they have attended any interviews recently and how do they feel about the same.
 - Rate negotiations, should ask for current pay rate & expected pay rate.
- Most of the recruiters do searches but titles-since every client have different terminology for different roles, so recruiters should spend some time undersatnding the requirment first.

- Recruiters do not keep information related to recruitment process handy.
- Violation of time zones while calling.

Dabur India Ltd., Ghaziabad (U.P.) currently provides RPO services to Fortune 500 companies. It has effected following aspects in a major way:

Cost Savings: Dabur India Ltd., Ghaziabad (U.P.) provides lower personnel costs (such as payroll, benefits, taxes, recruitment and training) and lower overhead (such as facilities, technology, maintenance, support and payroll processing.)

Quality Improvement: Dabur India Ltd., Ghaziabad (U.P.) engineers significant improvements in the quality of clients' business processes due to the expert staff involved, project management, the focus, and best practices utilized.

Educated Workforce: Dabur India Ltd., Ghaziabad (U.P.) enables its clients to take advantage of educated staff, improved training and a large pool of talent with 24/7 global support. Dabur India Ltd., Ghaziabad (U.P.) employees are fully trained on the recruitment procedures and industry and cultural knowledge of the target markets, such as the USA, the UK, Europe, etc.

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSION

Dabur India Ltd., Ghaziabad (U.P.), plays a very important and in INDIA (70-80%) is contract positions and all the major companies not only in INDIA but also in India, are totally dependent on recruitment firms to provide suitable candidates for the jobs vacant. Dabur India Ltd., Ghaziabad (U.P.) aims to provide quality and cost efficient manpower in a timely manner.

- Dabur India Ltd., Ghaziabad (U.P.) can improve time-to-hire- By outsourcing your recruitment process to Recruiting Junction, Dabur India Ltd., Ghaziabad (U.P.) companies can get access to a high quality of candidate pool. Employing a large number of resources, training them and managing them can consume a lot of their time. Dabur India Ltd., Ghaziabad (U.P.) can get companies high quality employees without any hassle of searching, finding, short-listing, negotiating, etc.

Dabur India Ltd., Ghaziabad (U.P.) gives managers the time to focus on other core HR activities- by outsourcing day-to-day recruitment activities managers can take out more time for strategic planning, daily operations, employee retention, training, and long-term people development initiatives.

Outsource the recruitment process through HR department of Dabur India Ltd., Ghaziabad (U.P.) and yet retain complete control- Dabur India Ltd., Ghaziabad (U.P.) recruiting junction can make it easier for firms to transfer non-core recruitment processes outside the enterprise while retaining full control of

information and workflows in a seamless, tightly integrated manner.

Increase recruitment cycle productivity- By outsourcing the recruitment process at low cost, companies get higher revenue and more time to do business development. Dabur India Ltd., Ghaziabad (U.P.) has refined processes that help you get staff quickly for your day-to-day and scaling needs.

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ANNEXURES

QUESTIONNAIRE

SECTION A (PERSONAL DETAILS)

- a) Organization working for-
- b) Designation-
- c) Age (Tick) : (i) 20- 40, (ii) 40-60, (iii) 60-Above
- d) Gender: Male/Female-

- e) Educational – (i) Grad-. (ii) Post grad-. (iii) Professional- Qualification
- f) Marital Status- Single/ Married
- g) No of Dependents-
- h) If married, No. of children-
- i) Work Experience: (i) Less than 2 yrs, (ii) 2-5yrs, (iii) 5-10yrs, (iv) More than 10 yrs.
- j) No. of yrs spent in other country/countries-
- k) Countries visited-

SECTION B

Following are certain statements that aim to identify the perceived role played by the HR department/HR Manager while sending an employee for international assignment. Please put a tick mark that best fits your opinion. The options for each statement are **SA**-Strongly Agree, **A**-Agree, **D**-Disagree and **SD**-Strongly disagree.

There is no right or wrong answers.

S.No	Statements	S A	A	D	S D
1	The HR Manager plays a potential role in motivating an employee to accept international assignments.				
2	The HR Manager, as a trainer facilitates the entire briefing of the process before sending of an employee for international assignments.				
3	The HR Manager must extensively train an expatriate before leaving and after reaching the new country.				
4	The HR manager plays the function of communicator in clearing doubts, issues and inhibitions (if there were any) before leaving.				
5	The HR Manager should also take care of the emotional aspects of an Expatriate.				
6	The HR Manager must prepare the Expatriate employee about the unforeseen challenges that may arise in the new country				
7	The HR Manager must generally brief about the ways and means to solve the issues that might arise in the other country.				
8	The HR dept must develop and provide training on various OD interventions which would help the Expatriates in managing the change and in adaptation to the new culture.				
9	Effective leadership by HR Manager determines success and failure of an Ex.				
10	The success of retaining the repatriates depends equally between the HR and the organization.				

SECTION C

This section aims to know the kinds of trainings that you received before going to the Host (New) country.

S. No	Kinds of training	Received	Somewhat received	Not received
1.	Technical training.(e.g. Process Training)			
2.	Training of new language.			
3.	Training related aspect that would give a deep insight into the Host/New country.			
a)	Social and business etiquettes			
b)	History and background.			
c)	Cultural values and priorities.			
d)	Geography and its major cities			
e)	Current affairs and relations the Host country and the parent country.			
f)	Religion and role of religion in daily life.			
g)	Different non verbal gestures used.(ex. To greet, wish etc.).			
h)	Laws & Rules/Regulations.			
i)	Political structure of the country.			
4.	Managerial skill development.			
a)	Motivation to work in new country.			
b)	Flexibility and adaptability.			
c)	Decision making skills.			
d)	Interpersonal skills.			
e)	Team building skills.			
f)	Cultural empathy.			
5.	Training related to practical aspects:-			
a)	Currency.			
b)	Transportation			

c)	Hours of business			
d)	Time zone.			
6.	Any other training received, please specify.			

Did the company also provided training to your family/spouse and children in adjusting to the new country?- Yes/No

If yes, answer the following mark answers for the following options, as done above.

1.	Training to spouse to adjust to new culture			
2.	Helping spouse find a job			
3.	Educational facilities for children			
4.	Housing facilities for family			
5.	Helping the parents back home(By providing special facilities)			

SECTION D

Following are the statements that represent the perception of the employee regarding the benefits of Expatriate training. Please put a tick mark that best fits your opinion. The options for each statement are **AI**-Always Important, **SI**-Somewhat Important, **RI**-Rarely Important, and **NI**-Not Important.

S. No	Statements	A I	SI	R I	N I
1.	Technical training is very important for Expatriates before taking up the assignment, as it results in higher performance.				
2.	To interact with people it is important to have good command over the local language.				
4.	Poor understanding of new social and business etiquettes can create problems and business losses.				
5.	Understanding of cultural values & their priorities helps in better adjustment.				
6.	Knowledge of different non verbal gestures (ex. To greet, wish etc.) that are used by them helps in better interaction with the locals of the country.				
7.	An Expatriate must carefully understand the Laws and Rule/ Regulations of the Host country.				
8.	Flexibility and adaptability are required to accommodate yourself to new country.				
9.	To understand people of the new country it is important to respect their culture and have cultural empathy.				

10.	Knowledge of their Currency is important to deal with financial issues.				
11.	Training should be given to spouse to adjust to the new culture.				
12.	Help should be given to spouse as well in finding a new job.				
13.	Educational facilities should be provided for children of Expatriates.				
14.	Company must also provide insurance facilities for the employee & family.				
15.	The parents back home should be helped by providing them special facilities.(Medical, financial, housing etc.)				